

Online Appendix to “Incentive-Compatible Peer-to-Peer Energy Trading on a Revocable-Access Settlement Substrate”

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Abstract— This online appendix accompanies the main paper and is self-contained. It gives the price-impact lemmas underlying the manipulation result, the full manipulation proof making the reserve-restoration condition explicit and bounding the no-restoration case, the formal substrate conditions, the full conditional incentive-compatibility proof, and the full large-population limit under hypotheses matching the main text. Cross-references “(main paper)” point to the numbered results in the main document.

I. PRICE-IMPACT LEMMAS

We work on the operating arc of Assumption 1 (main paper), on which $\underline{\kappa} \leq |p'(R)| \leq \bar{\kappa}$ and reserves stay in $[R, \bar{R}]$.

Lemma 1 (Impact of a single trade). *On the arc, a trade moving the energy reserve by x pays, relative to executing the whole quantity at the pre-trade price p_0 , an impact cost*

$$I(x) = \left| \int_0^x (p(R_e + t) - p_0) dt \right| \in \left[\frac{1}{2}\underline{\kappa}x^2, \frac{1}{2}\bar{\kappa}x^2 \right]. \quad (1)$$

Proof. By Assumption 1, $p(R_e + t) - p_0 = \int_0^t p'(R_e + u) du$ with $|p'| \in [\underline{\kappa}, \bar{\kappa}]$, so $|p(R_e + t) - p_0| \in [\underline{\kappa}t, \bar{\kappa}t]$. Integrating over $t \in [0, x]$ gives $I(x) \in [\int_0^x \underline{\kappa}t dt, \int_0^x \bar{\kappa}t dt] = [\frac{1}{2}\underline{\kappa}x^2, \frac{1}{2}\bar{\kappa}x^2]$. \square

Lemma 2 (Restoration and the split saving). *Suppose between successive parts of a partitioned trade the reserve returns to its pre-trade level R (the reserve-restoration condition). Then partitioning a quantity q into k equal parts has total impact $\frac{1}{2}s q^2/k$ for a slope $s \in [\underline{\kappa}, \bar{\kappa}]$, and the impact saving over a single trade is $\frac{1}{2}s(1 - k^{-1})q^2 \geq 0$. Define the restoration index $\rho \in [0, 1]$ as the fraction of the full-restoration saving actually realised by intervening flow; then the realised saving is $\rho \cdot \frac{1}{2}s(1 - k^{-1})q^2$ by definition, with $\rho = 1$ full restoration and $\rho = 0$ none.*

Proof. With full restoration each part of size q/k executes from the same pre-trade price, so by Lemma 1 (taking s as the local slope on the arc) it pays $\frac{1}{2}s(q/k)^2$, and the k parts pay $k \cdot \frac{1}{2}s(q/k)^2 = \frac{1}{2}s q^2/k$. The single trade pays $\frac{1}{2}s q^2$ by Lemma 1, so the saving is $\frac{1}{2}s(1 - k^{-1})q^2$. For the partial case we do not claim that a geometric reserve-recovery fraction implies a proportional saving on a general curved arc. Instead ρ is defined as the realised

fraction of the full-restoration saving, so the realised saving is $\rho \cdot \frac{1}{2}s(1 - k^{-1})q^2$ by construction. Monotonicity of per-part impact in the residual displacement (Lemma 1) guarantees the realised saving lies in $[0, \frac{1}{2}s(1 - k^{-1})q^2]$, so $\rho \in [0, 1]$ is well-defined. In the linear price-impact regime the realised index coincides with the geometric recovery fraction; for a strictly curved arc the two agree only to first order, which is why we index by realised saving rather than geometric recovery. \square

II. FULL MANIPULATION PROOF

Proposition 1 (Manipulability; full form). *Under Assumption 1 (main paper), in the bare market, for $|q_i| > 0$: (a) under reserve-restoration, splitting q_i into k equal parts presented as k identities yields gain $\Delta u_i = \frac{1}{2}s(1 - k^{-1})q_i^2 - kc_0$; with realised restoration index ρ the gain is $\rho \cdot \frac{1}{2}s(1 - k^{-1})q_i^2 - kc_0$; (b) wash-supply gains $(\bar{p}_i - c)(\hat{q}_i - q_i) - c_0$; (c) default gains $\bar{p}_i \hat{q}_i - C_i$.*

Proof. (a) The reserve-restoration condition is the arbitrage premise under which a CFMM tracks a reference price (Angeris and Chitra, 2020): arbitrageurs trade the gap created by each of i 's parts back to the reference, restoring R before the next part. Under restoration, Lemma 2 gives split impact $\frac{1}{2}s q_i^2/k$ and saving $\frac{1}{2}s(1 - k^{-1})q_i^2$; netting the k identities' fixed cost kc_0 gives the stated gain. The partial-restoration gain follows from the realised-index definition in Lemma 2. Feasibility: no primitive links the k identities to one meter, and the per-identity price guarantee of Angeris and Chitra (2020) concerns each identity separately, not their aggregate. (b) Presenting $\hat{q}_i \neq q_i$ has revenue $\bar{p}_i \hat{q}_i$ and cost $C_i(\hat{q}_i, q_i) = c|\hat{q}_i - q_i| + c_0$; the gain over truthful presentation is $(\bar{p}_i - c)(\hat{q}_i - q_i) - c_0$. (c) Non-delivery removes delivery cost, leaving gain $\bar{p}_i \hat{q}_i - C_i$, positive when unpenalised. \square

III. SUBSTRATE CONDITIONS

Assumption 1 (Admission injectivity). *The map from connection points to certificates is injective and double-issuance is publicly detectable (Definition 1, main paper); the identity set of each meter has size one.*

Assumption 2 (Commitment binding under T2). *At settlement the committed aggregate is a deterministic*

function of i 's signed records and, by trust assumption T2 (meter integrity, main paper), equals the physical net flow q_i ; an inconsistent presentation is rejected (Definition 2, main paper).

Assumption 3 (Bond dominance). *The admitted position is capped at the rated capacity \bar{q}_i and the arc price is bounded by \bar{p} , so the maximum single-period payment is $\bar{p}\bar{q}_i$; the bond satisfies $\Pi > \bar{p}\bar{q}_i$ (Definition 3, main paper).*

IV. FULL INCENTIVE-COMPATIBILITY PROOF

Theorem 1 (Conditional dominance; full form). *Under Assumptions 1–3 and aggregate per-interval clearing, presenting the true committed position $\hat{q}_i = q_i$ maximises u_i among quantity-reporting deviations for every prosumer i and every profile of others' strategies, every cleared trade is settlement-enforced, and the gains of Proposition 1 are non-positive. The result is conditional on T2, does not establish meter-to-physical fidelity, and does not treat cross-interval storage strategies.*

Proof. Fix i and an arbitrary profile of others' strategies. *Split-metering.* By Assumption 1 the only admissible k is 1, at which the saving $\frac{1}{2}s(1 - k^{-1})q_i^2$ vanishes; the partial-restoration gain is likewise zero at $k = 1$. The construction is infeasible. *Wash-supply.* By Assumption 2 the settlement check recomputes the committed aggregate, which equals q_i under T2; any $\hat{q}_i \neq q_i$ is rejected and yields payoff 0, so $\hat{q}_i = q_i$ weakly dominates, at which $C_i = 0$. *Default.* By Assumption 3, $\Pi > \bar{p}\bar{q}_i \geq \bar{p}_i\hat{q}_i$ for every admissible trade, so the default net $\bar{p}_i\hat{q}_i - \Pi < 0$; delivery strictly dominates. *Residual.* With the three quantity-reporting deviations removed, i 's admissible set among them is presenting its single committed interval position with $\hat{q}_i = q_i$. Within-interval order timing is not an available deviation under aggregate per-interval clearing: the interval position is netted and priced once, so it cannot reproduce the interleaving the split exploited. The only admissible interval report is the committed metered aggregate q_i : inconsistent reports are rejected (Assumption 2) and no second identity exists (Assumption 1), so truthful presentation is the only feasible interval action, at zero discrepancy cost. The price-reporting guarantee of Angeris and Chitra (2020) bears only on price formation for the resulting single trade, not on the meter-to-market binding. As this holds for every profile of others' actions, $\hat{q}_i = q_i$ is dominant among quantity-reporting deviations, and every cleared trade is backed by a committed meter (Assumption 2) and a dominant bond (Assumption 3). The wash-supply step is the only one using T2, and it binds report to meter, not meter to physical flow; cross-interval storage strategies lie outside the deviation class. \square

V. FULL LARGE-POPULATION LIMIT

Proposition 2 (Truthfulness in the limit; full form). *Let true positions q_1, \dots, q_n be i.i.d. with finite second moment and law $\text{law}(q)$, let $m_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i \delta_{q_i}$, and let the CFMM*

marginal price be a bounded, weakly continuous functional $p[\cdot]$ of m_n . Under Assumptions 1–3, the unique dominant action of every prosumer is $\hat{q}_i = q_i$ for every n and every realisation of $(q_j)_{j \neq i}$; hence $m_n \Rightarrow m^ = \text{law}(q)$ almost surely and $p[m_n] \rightarrow p[m^*] =: p^*$, a deterministic limit.*

Proof. *Step 1.* By Theorem 1, $\hat{q}_i = q_i$ is dominant for each i and every profile of others' actions; the argument removes the three deviations without reference to n or to the distribution of others' actions, so the quantifier is uniform in n and $\hat{q}_i = q_i$ is dominant for every population size. *Step 2.* Hence $m_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i \delta_{q_i}$; the q_i are i.i.d. with finite second moment, so by Glivenko–Cantelli and the strong law $m_n \Rightarrow \text{law}(q) = m^*$ almost surely in the weak topology. *Step 3.* Weak continuity and boundedness of $p[\cdot]$ give $p[m_n] \rightarrow p[m^*] = p^*$ almost surely; m^* is non-random, so the limit is deterministic. No self-consistency fixed point is invoked: the action is determined before the price, not jointly with it. The continuity of $p[\cdot]$ is a hypothesis, a regularity condition on the price functional, and is not derived here. \square

Remark 1. *This is sharper than a standard mean-field game only because Step 1 makes the optimal action invariant to m ; the fixed-point problem $m = \text{BR}(m)$ that may be non-unique in general is here trivial. It does not establish existence in a model where the action depends on m , and in particular says nothing about the Markov-perfect mean-field game of Fabi et al. (2025), whose equilibrium is genuinely a fixed point.*

REFERENCES

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